

Strategic plan for co-ordination of the National Food Administration's EFSA work 2009-2012

Case

Process Questions: What should we be thinking about and decide on?

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Current Situation

Process questions: What has happened, where are we today and what insights have we got? What do we think about the future?

Insights from the analysis of the current situation:
<i>From outside and in:</i>
- EFSA would like for closer scientific co-operation and collaboration with the Member States and needs e.g. expanded scientific networks of Member States. It is important that we continue to give priority to co-operation.
- Sweden should increase its co-operation and engagement with the EFSA and further develop the working structure.
- NFA is appreciated as a partner by EFSA.
- In 2007 EFSA established and funded in part, a contact point, "Focal Point" (FP), in each Member State. The Focal Point should be a link between EFSA and all relevant actors and stakeholders in the Member States. NFA will receive € 25,000 in 2009.
- EFSA has expressed its satisfaction with our work as FP.
- NFA will continue to make visible, promote and provide information on EFSA, EFSA's mandate and tasks to the Swedish authorities, research organizations, professional organisations, stakeholders and consumers.
- The collaboration between Sweden's representative to the advisory group, Advisory Forum (AF), and FP is working well.
- Our sister agencies, the National Veterinary Institute (SVA), the Swedish Board of Agriculture (SJV) and the Swedish Chemicals Agency (KemI), wants more targeted information on what is going on within the EFSA and the AF. We will further develop the structure.
<i>From inside and out:</i>
- The AF has defined the role and specified the tasks for the FP. Together with the AF and EFSA (Scientific Co-operation) we will continue the development. Increased resources are required to further develop the FP.
- Internal procedures for EFSA work needs to be further developed. Information dissemination within the NFA on EFSA's activities, assignments, etc. will be further structured.
- An internal group for information exchange consisting of the AF, the Communications

Div., the IT Div., the Nutrition Dpt. and the Head of the R&D Dpt., EFSA experts and FP has been established within the NFA. This group convenes after each AF session.
- It is scientifically very rewarding to participate in EFSA's work. It is valuable for the NFA.
- It is costly to participate in EFSA's work.
- We have good coverage of EFSA's activities –within new fields, etc. We need to increase the efforts to engage and activate more Swedish national experts.
- We will continue to chart the Swedish § 36-organization skills and areas of interest - and engage and propose new Swedish organizations, research, networking and national experts for working groups, networks, interaction meetings, hearings, etc.
- EFSA's strategic plans are not taken into account in NFA internal planning. Prioritization of risk assessment in support of EFSA's work is not handled in this plan.

Vision

Process Question: How do we want our world to look?

The vision and values of the National Food Administration are also valid for this plan.

Vision of the National Food Administration:

"All consumers feel good of the food"

We want all consumers to feel good both physically and mentally, in both short and long term. We share our vision with other co-actors.

Values

Process question: How should we treat each other?

Values of the National Food Administration:

Respect

We have respect for each other and for the decisions taken.

Positive attitude

We show a positive attitude, which together with our critical review approach promote creativity, commitment and responsibility for the whole.

Openness

We have an open and honest working environment that promotes interaction between individuals and between areas of activities.

Comment: Our values are valid for all internal and external relationships.

Purpose

Process Question: What should we be doing, why and for whom, in order to to

contribute to our vision?

We will monitor, interact, make visible, co-ordinate and integrate EFSA's work both internally and externally to enable Sweden to support, influence and benefit from EFSA's work.

Focus

Process Question: What should we, in our view, focus on to become appreciated and successful?

The EFSA focus of work 2009-2012

- There should be clear link between EFSA's plans and the NFA strategic plan in relevant areas
- Make the importance of EFSA's work visible through the NFA website
- Continue to develop networks of Swedish research and competent EFSA organizations for optimal interaction with the EFSA
- Provide information and communication internally and externally on the work of EFSA and EFSA's Advisory Forum (AF)
- Act to involve other competent authorities in EFSA's work (through the Consultative Group)
- Increase the external and internal financing of the Focal Point

Goal

Process question: What should we therefore achieve?

Goals of the National Food Administration

- A. The food is safe for the consumer
- B. Eating habits are good
- C. Food handling is honest
- D. The NFA is perceived in Sweden and abroad as credible, prompt, responsive and proactive
- E. NFA is one of Sweden's best workplaces

<i>Goals of EFSA's work 2009-2012</i>	<i>State which main NFA goal the goal belongs to (A-E)</i>
<i>Goal 1:</i> EFSA is pleased with how the NFA works as FP.	A, B, D
<i>Goal 2:</i> The competent national authorities, and § 36 organizations are happy with the NFA participation in EFSA's Advisory Group.	A, B, D
<i>Goal 3:</i> NFA takes part of the skill and experience that collaborates involved in EFSA's activities bring back to the Administration	A, B
<i>Goal 4:</i> EFSA carries out risk assessments, which are valuable to the NFA and Sweden.	A, B
<i>Goal 5:</i> Sweden carries out risk assessments that are important to EFSA.	A, D
<i>Goal 6:</i> EFSA's planned activities are well known and are the basis for the NFA operational planning.	A, B

Activities 2009-2012

Process question: What should we be doing, and when, in order to achieve our goals?

Goal	Activity	When?	Competence	Manager
1	Further develop the EFSA/Focal Point website to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • make visible and market EFSA • facilitate information exchange with and between Swedish EFSA authorities and Swedish research, institutions, organizations and other stakeholders. • facilitate exchange of information with EFSA 	2009	Communications Division, IT Division	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede
1	Develop a country profile that describes how the Swedish authorities involved in the food chain are organized. Work is conducted as an ESCO project.	During 2009	Ministry of Agriculture, Swedish authorities involved in the food chain	Anita Strömberg
1	Develop working procedures for FP, including responsibilities and authority, both internally and externally	During 2009	Leif Busk, Katarina Hörnfeldt Olson	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede
1,2,3	Update the list of Swedish organizations authorized to carry out EFSA assignments (so-called Article 36 organizations) and organize annual meetings of the Article 36 Network	Running	Head of Dpt. and Heads of Divisions of the NFA R & D Dpt., Leif Busk, other EFSA authorities, Ministry of Agriculture, national research etc.	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede
1	Contribute to the establishment of an expert database of scientific experts in Europe (including providing information on the database and to facilitate and assist the experts in the expression of interest).	Running	Head of Dpt. and Heads of Divisions of the NFA Research and Development Dpt., Leif Busk, national research etc.	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede
1	Improve the EFSA Information Exchange Platform. Publish NFA risk assessments.	During 2009	Leif Busk, Head of Dpt. and Heads of Divisions of the NFA R & D Dpt.,	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede
1	Provide targeted information on EFSA to the NFA departments and divisions.	During 2009	Leif Busk	Anita Strömberg
2	Invite competent national authorities and Swedish EFSA experts to an annual meeting to agree on the Swedish EFSA-work	Meeting spring 2009	Leif Busk, Katarina Hörnfeldt Olson	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede
2	Participate in the advisory group meetings	Running	Ministry of Agriculture, sister authorities in the food chain, the NFA Executive Committee, the Executive Committee of the R&D Dpt., the group of scientific advisors	Leif Busk
4	Bring forward proposals for key areas that EFSA should engage in to promote Swedish interests.	Before EFSA's short- and long-term planning	Heads of Dpts. and Divisions of the NFA Nutrition and R&D Dpts., Leif Busk, sister authorities, competent organizations, other	Anita Strömberg Lars Jorhede Busk, Katarina Hörnfeldt Olson

			stakeholders	
6	Bring forward proposals for key areas that the NFA should engage in to support EFSA	Running, before the executive meeting in June	Anita Strömberg, the group of scientific advisors	Heads of and Division the Nutrition R&D Dept
6	Bring forward proposals for key areas that Sweden should engage in to support EFSA	During EFSA's short- and long-term planning process	Heads of Dpts. and Divisions of the NFA Nutrition and R&D Dpts., Leif Busk, sister authorities, competent organizations, other stakeholders	Anita Strömberg, Lars Jorh, Busk, Katarina Hörnfeldt
6	Participate in the EFSA/AF project group on IT	Running	IT Division	Örjan Olsson
6	Participate in the EFSA/AF project group on consumption data	Running	Nutrition Dpt.	Heléne Engberg, Barbieri
6	Participate in the EFSA/AF project group on communication	Running	Communications Div.	Eva Corp
6	Participate in the EFSA/AF project group on microbiological risk assessment	Running	Microbiology Div.	Roland L

Competence

Process Question: Which competence do we need and how do we ensure it?
See the "Activity" column above.

External relations (?)

Process Question: With whom should we co-operate and in what way?

Relations	What shall we do?	Manager
The Ministry of Agriculture	Regular information before and after AF-meetings, information via e-mail, annual meetings, informal contacts	Leif Busk, Katarina Hörnfeldt, Örjan Olsson
Competent authorities, especially the Swedish Board of Agriculture, the National Veterinary Institute, the Swedish Chemicals Agency and the Swedish Board of Fisheries	Regular information before and after AF meetings, annual meetings, e-mail, informal contacts	Leif Busk, Anita Strömberg
Swedish competent organizations (so-called Article 36 organizations), other scientific excellence and individual experts	Information via e-mail, invitations to annual meetings	Anita Strömberg
EFSA	Participation in the AF, FP meetings, panels, meetings, networking, e-mail, informal contacts	Leif Busk, Anita Strömberg, Eva Corp, Örjan Olsson, EFSA experts etc.
Other Member States	Networking, meetings, informal contacts, e-mail	Leif Busk, Anita Strömberg, Director General
Internal and external EFSA experts	Networking, meetings, informal contacts, e-mail	Anita Strömberg

Marianne Elvander, member of the EFSA Management Board	Networking, meetings, informal contacts, e-mail	Leif Busk
Other stakeholders (eg, consumer organizations, food industry , etc.)	Networking, meetings, informal contacts, e-mail	Anita Strömberg

Organization and interaction

Process Question: Who will be responsible for what and how do we interact?

Organization of task

Activity	When?	Manager
Ensure the NFA's mandate and role of the EFSA Focal Point	Running	Director General
Strengthen the Focal Point in the NFA	2009	AC, R&D Dpt.
Report to the Ministry of Agriculture after each meeting of the Consultative Group	Running	Leif Busk
Develop the EFSA webb/forum on the NFA website	Running	Communications Div., Anita Strömberg, website editor
Invite the competent authorities and organizations and Swedish EFSA experts to meetings	Annually	Leif Busk, Anita Strömberg
Use of EFSA's extranet	Running	Leif Busk, Örjan Olsson
Internal information and education drive	Running	Anita Strömberg
Further develop the internal EFSA group and its role	2009	Katarina Hörnfeldt Olsson, Leif Busk, Anita Strömberg
Review EFSA's Management Plan and evaluate the need for contributions through AF	Annually before head meetings in June/September	Anita Strömberg, conce Head of Divisions and NFA Executive Commi
Review the list of Swedish Article 36 organizations	Annually	Anita Strömberg

Economic impact

Process Question: What costs and investments will this lead to? How much capital will we need and how do we acquire it?

Expected costs associated with

- *development and subsequent maintenance of the website (web editor)*
- *the creation of FP (funded by EFSA, approximately SEK 275 000 + possible needs of additional resources) – SEK 500 000*
- *other costs -5-10 000 SEK (mainly annual meetings with other EFSA authorities)*

Follow-up

Process Question: What should we follow up, when and how?

Follow-up of goals:

What should be	How?	When (frequency)?	Manager
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monitored?			
Goal 1-6	In Linus	3 times per year	Katarina Hörnfeldt Olson

Follow-up of activities:

Activities	How?	When?	Manager
Goal 1-17	In Linus	3 times per year	Katarina Hörnfeldt Olson
Plan	Revision	Spring 2010	Anita Strömberg